

An Exploratory Study to Identify the Perceived Stress and Coping Abilities of Primary Dysmenorrhea among Adolescent Girls in Nandhanar Girls Higher Secondary School, Chidambaram

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How to cite this paper: Dr. Jeyalakshmi. S | Mrs. Kalaiyarasi. D | Mrs. Bharathi. S "An Exploratory Study to Identify the Perceived Stress and Coping Abilities of Primary Dysmenorrhea among Adolescent Girls in Nandhanar Girls Higher Secondary School, Chidambaram" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-3, April 2019, pp.235-238, URL: <http://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd21709.pdf>

IJTSRD21709

ABSTRACT

Primary dysmenorrhoea, which affects from 43 to 91% of adolescent girls, is defined as painful uterine cramps that precede and accompany menses. Paediatricians and gynaecologists should thus be more actively involved in the diagnosis of adolescent primary dysmenorrhoea. The present study aimed to assess the stress and coping among adolescent girls during menstrual period. Descriptive research design was used, convenience sampling technique used. Results showed that adolescents girls had (7%) inadequate coping, (76%) moderate coping, (17%) adequate coping during their menstruation and had (4%) mild stress, (17%) moderate stress, (79%) severe stress during their menstruation, there was no significant association between the coping of the subjects and the selected demographic variables. Thus the selected hypothesis (H1) was rejected.

Keywords: Primary dysmenorrhoea, stress, coping

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INTRODUCTION

Adolescents are the nation's future. Their good health sums the nation's resource. These resources must be protected, promoted and maintained by the health care professional in various sector. The government of India has formulated many healthcare services for adolescents' good health. Yet solutions are required for the minor issues, which can be dealt and managed at home before the situation worsens. Adolescents with age 10-19 yrs constitute about one fifth of India's population and young people aged 10-24 yrs account for about one third of the population.

Generally, the term "adolescents" refers to the individual between the ages of 10-19 years and the term "youth" refers to individuals between ages of 15-24 years, while "young people" covers the entire age group ranging from 10-24 years (UNFPA / WHO / UNICEF, 1989). The term "Puberty" means morphological, physiological and psychological changes occurring in the growing girls and boys, as the gonads change from the infertile to the adult state. Adolescence is classified based on the growth and sexual

development into early adolescence, middle adolescence and late adolescence.

This primary dysmenorrhoea is highly prevalent among the sample of adolescents and young adults and is related to school absenteeism. Thus, health care providers should regularly screen for dysmenorrhoea and offer appropriate treatment.

Similarly **Anil (2010)** conducted an experimental survey to identify the prevalence of severity of dysmenorrhoea and its associated symptoms among adolescent girls between 15 - 20 yrs studying in higher secondary schools (Pre-University Colleges) of Gwalior. The result showed that the prevalence of dysmenorrhoea in adolescent girls was found to be 79.67%. Most of them, (37.96%) suffered regularly from severe dysmenorrhoea. The three most common symptoms present on the day before and first day of menstruation were lethargy and tiredness, depression and inability to concentrate in work.

Statement of the Problem

“An exploratory study to identify the perceived stress and coping abilities of primary dysmenorrhea among adolescent girls in Nandhanar Girls Higher Secondary School, Chidambaram.

Objectives:

1. To assess the level of perceived stress among girls with primary dysmenorrhea
2. To assess the coping ability among girls with primary dysmenorrhea.
3. To correlate the perceived stress and coping ability among girls with primary dysmenorrhea.
4. To associate the perceived stress and coping abilities with selected demographic variables.

Hypotheses:

H₁: There will be significant association between perceived stress with selected demographic variable.

Assumptions

1. Dysmenorrhea (pain menstruation) may induce higher level of stress among adolescent girls
2. Higher level of stress may affect the coping ability of adolescent girls

Delimitation

1. The study is delimited to adolescent girls studying 11th standard during the academic year 2018-2019 only.

2. Data collection period was 3 days.
3. This study is limited to girls with age group of 16-18 years.
4. The study was restricted to assess only pain, stress, coping ability about primary dysmenorrhoea.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Research approach:

The research approach chosen for the study was the quantitative approach.

Research design:

The design adopted for the study was descriptive research design.

Variables:

Stress and coping among the adolescent girls during menstrual period.

Setting of the study:

The government Nandanar girls higher secondary school, Chidambaram, Cuddalore district.

Population:

The adolescent girls studying 11th standard between the age group 15-17 yrs.

Target population:

The adolescent girls who are attained menarche.

SCHEMATIC REPRESENTATION OF THE RESEARCH DESIGN

Sample:

Adolescent girls having primary dysmenorrhea from the Nandhanar girls higher secondary school Chidambaram, Cuddalore.

Sample size:

The sample size consisted of 70 students studying in 11th standard students from government Nandhanar girls higher secondary school, Chidambaram, Cuddalore district.

Sampling technique:

Convenience sampling technique was used followed. 70 samples were selected on the basis of the inclusion Criteria.

Criteria for sample selection:

Inclusion criteria:

Adolescent girls who were:

- Attained menarche.
- Having primary dysmenorrhea.
- between the age group of 15-17 years
- Willing to participate.
- Understand Tamil or English.

Exclusion criteria:

- Sick or leave on the day of data collection

Description of the data collection instrument:

Section - 1

This part assessed the demographic variables such as age, gender, educational status, occupation, family income per month, religion, residence, by using structured questions

Section-2

Part-I the tool used for the data collection was modified echelefoulosiane de coping scale.

Description of the scale:

Echelefoulosiane de coping scale used to assess the coping abilities.

Scoring procedure:

The correct answer was scored as '0'

Wrong answer was scored as '1'

Total score was 40.

S.No	Coping level	Percentage
1.	Inadequate coping	50%
2.	Moderate coping	50%-75%
3.	Adequate coping	75%

Part-II

The tool used for data collection was modified stress assessment scale.

Description of the scale:

Modified stress assessment scale used to assess the stress level.

Scoring procedure:

The correct answer was scored as '0'

Wrong answer was scored as '1'

Total score was 40.

S.No	Stress level	Percentage
1.	Mild stress	50%
2.	Moderate stress	50-75%
3.	Severe stress	75%

RESULTS:

Table-2: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Level of Coping among Adolescent Girls (N = 70)

Level of Coping	No.	%
Inadequate coping (<50%)	5	7.0
Moderately adequate coping (50-75%)	53	76.0
Adequate coping (>75%)	12	17.0

Table 2 shows 5(7.0%) of the adolescent girls had inadequate coping, 53(76.0%) had moderately adequate coping and 12(17.0%) had adequate coping.

Figure - 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Level of stress among Adolescent Girls

Table 4: Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation of stress and coping among Selected Adolescent Girls (N = 70)

	Mean	Standard Deviation	'r' value	P value
Coping	7.24	5.19	0.107	0.001
Stress	21.04	6.04		

S - Significant

Table 4 shows that the coping mean was 7.24 with a standard deviation of 5.19. whereas the stress mean was 21.04 with a standard deviation of 6.04. Thus the difference in the mean was confirmed by the period 'r' value 0.107 which was found to be significant P < 0.001 level.

DISCUSSION:

In the present study, the researcher had taken the adolescents' dysmenorrhoea as a main variable to find out the stress and coping abilities of the adolescent girls who are having primary dysmenorrhoea. Many literature and research findings highlighted that, even though the menstruation is biological occurrences during a women reproductive life, approximately 90% of them experienced one or more symptoms of dysmenorrhoea during menstruation or just before menstruation. Dysmenorrhoea is the most common problem present among the adolescent girls. Currently the researcher has undertaken the study entitled 'to assess the

prevalence and perceived stress of primary dysmenorrhoea among the adolescent girls in selected schools at cuddalore district.

The findings of the current study suggested, that the perceived stress and coping abilities of primary dysmenorrhoea in adolescent girls. This study was conducted into 2 phases. Phase I was done in part A. Part A was a descriptive survey study, which was conducted to identify the prevalence of primary dysmenorrhoea and perceived stress due to primary dysmenorrhoea among 70 adolescent girls who attained menarche from selected schools at Cuddalore district. This was assessed by the structured primary dysmenorrhoea rating scale, and adolescent stress scale on primary dysmenorrhoea.

In phase II, 70 Study Subjects were selected from Phase I by using non- probability purposive sampling technique.

Primary dysmenorrhoea and perceived stress of primary dysmenorrhoea was common among the adolescent girls, which was identified during the descriptive survey of present study. Adolescent girls were managing their menstrual pain and stress with medications and many of them took leave to school and stayed at home.

CONCLUSION:

The study results indicated that adolescent girls obtained. The prevalence of primary dysmenorrhoea among adolescent girls are also high and the level of perceived stress of primary dysmenorrhoea also seems to be high among them.

During adolescent period itself in order to promote the physical health, mental health, reproductive health of the adolescent.

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